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SYNTHESIS AND ANTIMICROBIAL ACTIVITY OF NOVEL PYRROLYL PYRAZOLINE METHANONE DERIVATIVES

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ABSTRACT

Novel pyrrolyl-pyrazoline methanone derivatives (5a-j) were synthesized by reacting mixture of substituted quinoline chalcones (3a-j) and 4-pyrrol-1yl benzoic acid hydrazide (4) in ethanol. The reaction mixture was heated under reflux for 16 h on a water bath followed by addition of ice cold water at room temperature and mixture was kept overnight resulting in the formations of substituted pyrrolyl-pyrazoline methanone derivatives. Purity of newly synthesized compounds were confirmed by TLC and melting point. The structure of the all newly synthesized compounds were confirmed by spectral study such as IR, ¹H NMR and Mass spectroscopy. The title compounds were screened for their antibacterial and antitubercular activities.

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INTRODUCTION

Tuberculosis (TB) is the most airborne contagious disease caused by *Mycobacterium tuberculosis* (MTB) and is the second leading cause of death from an infectious disease worldwide, after the human immunodeficiency virus (HIV). TB is known to be one of the major causes of death in HIV patients. According to the World Health Organization (WHO), 8.7 million people were infected with TB in 2011 resulting in the death of 1.4 million people. Furthermore, about 0.43 million deaths due to TB were reported amongst people affected HIV. In 2011 almost 60% of Multidrug Resistant-TB (MDR-TB) cases were reported from India, China and Russian federation only. The MTB commonly attacks the lungs, kidney, spine, and brain. Hence, if TB is not treated properly, it can be serious and fatal [1].

Despite *Bacillus Calmette Guerin* (BCG) vaccine and the use of combined chemotherapy with first-line (isoniazid, ethambutol, rifampicin, pyrazinamide) or second-line (ethionamide, ciprofloxacin, moxi-floxacin) antibiotics, MTB is the agent which causes more deaths from infection in the world. Also significant lack of patient adherence to long-term therapy leads to the emergence of multidrug-resistant (MDR). Hence, the discovery of fast-acting effective new drugs to effectively combat TB, including multidrug resistant tuberculosis, is imperative.

Pyrazoles and their variously substituted derivatives are important biological agents and a significant amount of research activity has been directed towards this class. In particular, they are used as antitumor [2], antibacterial, antifungal, antiviral, antiparasitic, antitubercular and insecticidal agents [3-6]. Some of these compounds have also anti-inflammatory, anti-diabetic, anesthetic and analgesic properties [7-10].

Pyrroles are found to be as the fundamental structural motifs in various classes of natural and biologically important molecules such as porphyrins, bile pigments, coenzymes and alkaloids. This moiety is also present in several synthetic pharmaceuticals as well as electrically conducting polymers [11]. Pyrrole and its derivatives have shown to possess biological activities such as antibacterial [12], antitumor [13], analgesic [14], antitubercular [15-16], anti-inflammatory and antiallergic [17].

As per the above findings, we came to know that pyrrole and pyrazolines containing heterocyclic compounds are useful chemical entities because of their wide range of biological applications. Keeping in view, we thought of combining pyrrole and pyrazoline moieties and analyzing their antitubercular and antimicrobial activity.

Experimental

Melting points were determined using the Shital-digital programmable melting point apparatus and are uncorrected. FTIR spectra in KBr pellets were recorded on a Bruker FTIR spectrophotometer. The ^1H spectra were recorded on a Bruker AVANCE II at 400 MHz, chemical shifts are expressed in parts per million (ppm) relative to TMS. The abbreviations used to describe the peak patterns are: (b) broad, (s) singlet, (d) doublet, (t) triplet, (q) quartet, and (m) multiplet. Mass spectra (MS) were recorded in a JEOL GC/MATE II GC-Mass spectrometer and Shimadzu QP 20105 GC-Mass spectrometer. Analytical thin-layer chromatography (TLC) was performed on precoated TLC sheets of silica gel 60 F₂₅₄ (Merck, Darmstadt, Germany) visualized by long- and short- wavelength ultraviolet (UV) lamps.

Synthesis of 2-chloroquinoline-3-carbaldehyde (1)

Dimethylformamide 9.6 ml (0.125 mol) was cooled to 0 °C and phosphoryl chloride 32.2 ml (0.35 mol) was added drop wise with stirring. To this solution acetanilide (0.05 mol) were added and after 5 min the solution was heated under reflux at 75 °C for 16.5 h and cooled. The reaction mixture was poured into ice-water (300 ml) and stirred for 30 min at 0-10 °C. The 2-chloroquinoline-3-carbaldehyde were filtered off, washed with water (100 ml), dried, recrystallized from ethyl acetate, yield is 68%, M.P-146-148 °C.

General procedure for synthesis of 3-(2-chloroquinolin-3-yl)-1-substituted phenylprop-2-en-1-ones (3 a-i)

A solution of sodium hydroxide (40%) in water and rectified spirit was cooled at 0-10 °C. Appropriate acetophenone (0.005 mol) was added with constant stirring then quinolone carbaldehyde (0.005 mol) was added to the solution. The temperature of mixture was kept at about 25 °C and stirred vigorously until the mixture was thick enough to retard stirring (4 h). The mixture was kept at 8 °C overnight. The product was filtered, washed with cold water until washings were neutral to litmus and further washed with ice cold ethanol. The crude product was recrystallized from ethanol.

Synthesis of 4-(1H-pyrrol-1-yl)benzoic acid hydrazide (4)

Synthesis of compound 4 was carried out by procedure described by Joshi *et al* [18], a mixture of ethyl 4-pyrrol-1-yl benzoate (3.22 g, 0.015 mol) with hydrazine hydrate (10 mL) in absolute ethanol (10 mL) was refluxed for 3 h. The reaction mixture was cooled and crystalline mass obtained was recrystallized from ethanol and obtained as yellow crystals in 74% yield. M.P-180-182°C.

General procedure for the synthesis of (4-(1H-pyrrole-1-yl)phenyl) (5-substituted phenyl-3 phenyl -4,5-dihydro-1H-pyrrole) methanones (5a-j)

In a mixture of appropriate chalcones (3a-j) (0.01mol) in methanol, 4-(1H-pyrrole-1-yl)benzohydrazide (**4**) (0.01mol) was added in a round bottom flask. The reaction mixture was heated under reflux for 16 h on a water bath followed by addition of ice cold water at room temperature. The mixture was then kept overnight at 8°C. The precipitate was filtered, washed with distilled water and dried. The crude crystals were recrystallized from ethanol.

(4-(1H-pyrrol-1-yl)phenyl)(5-(2-chloroquinolin-3-yl)-3-phenyl-4,5-dihydro-1H-pyrazol-1-yl)methanone (5a):

IR (KBr) ν_{\max} , cm^{-1} : 3057 (Ar-H), 1665 (C=O), 1606 (C=N); $^1\text{H NMR}$ (400 MHz, DMSO- d_6) δ (ppm): 1.41 (s, 2H, pyrazoline-C₄-H), 2.34 (s, 1H, pyrazoline-C₃-H), 6.39 (s, 2H, pyrrole-C₃, C₄-H), 7.18-7.90 (m, 15H, pyrrole C₂, C₅-H; bridging ph-C₂, C₃, C₅, C₆-H; quinoline-C₄, C₅, C₆, C₇, C₈-H and ph-C₂, C₃, C₄, C₅, C₆-H). MS (EI): m/z = found 476.20[M⁺]; calcd. 476.96.

(4-(1H-pyrrol-1-yl)phenyl)(3-(4-bromophenyl)-5-(2-chloroquinolin-3-yl)-4,5-dihydro-1H-pyrazol-1-yl)methanone (5b)

IR (KBr) ν_{\max} , cm^{-1} : 2955 (Ar-H), 1664 (C=O), 1606 (C=N); $^1\text{H NMR}$ (400 MHz, DMSO- d_6) δ (ppm): 1.68 (s, 2H, pyrazoline-C₄-H), 2.31 (s, 1H pyrazoline-C₃-H), 6.40 (s, 2H, pyrrole-C₃, C₄-H), 6.99-8.24 (m, 15H, pyrrole C₂, C₅-H; bridging ph-C₂, C₃, C₅, C₆-H; quinoline-C₄, C₅, C₆, C₇, C₈-H and ph-C₂, C₃, C₅, C₆-H). MS (EI): m/z = found 555.09 [M⁺]; calcd. 555.86.

(4-(1H-pyrrol-1-yl)phenyl)(5-(2-chloroquinolin-3-yl)-3-(4-nitrophenyl)-4,5-dihydro-1H-pyrazol-1-yl)methanone (5c):

IR (KBr) ν_{\max} , cm^{-1} : 3230 (Ar-H), 1643 (C=O), 1606 (C=N); $^1\text{H NMR}$ (400 MHz, DMSO- d_6) δ (ppm): 1.74 (t, 2H, pyrazoline-C₄-H), 2.28 (s, 1H pyrazoline-C₃-H), 6.89 (s, 2H, pyrrole-C₃, C₄-H), 7.00-7.97 (m, 15H, pyrrole C₂, C₅-H; bridging ph-C₂, C₃, C₅, C₆-H; quinoline-C₄, C₅, C₆, C₇, C₈-H and ph-C₂, C₃, C₅, C₆-H).

(4-(1H-pyrrol-1-yl)phenyl)(5-(2-chloroquinolin-3-yl)-3-(4-methoxyphenyl)-4,5-dihydro-1H-pyrazol-1-yl)methanone (5d):

IR (KBr) ν_{\max} , cm^{-1} : 3060 (Ar-H), 1669 (C=O), 1603 (C=N). $^1\text{H NMR}$ (400 MHz, DMSO- d_6) δ (ppm): 3.55 (s, 2H, pyrazoline-C₄-H), 3.81 (m, 3H, OCH₃-H) 3.91 (s, 1H pyrazoline-C₃-H), 6.32 (m, 2H, pyrrole-C₃, C₄-H), 6.38-7.99 (m, 15H, pyrrole C₂, C₅-H; bridging ph-C₂, C₃, C₅, C₆-H; quinoline-C₄, C₅, C₆, C₇, C₈-H and ph-C₂, C₃, C₅, C₆-H).

(4-(1H-pyrrol-1-yl)phenyl)(3-(4-chlorophenyl)-5-(2-chloroquinolin-3-yl)-4,5-dihydro-1H-pyrazol-1-yl)methanone (5e):

IR (KBr) ν_{\max} , cm^{-1} : 3060 (Ar-H), 1667 (C=O), 1606 (C=N). $^1\text{H NMR}$ (400 MHz, DMSO- d_6) δ (ppm): 1.62 (s, 2H, pyrazoline-C₄-H), 3.26 (s, 1H pyrazoline-C₃-H), 6.40 (s, 2H, pyrrole-C₃, C₄-H), 6.93-8.39 (m, 15H, pyrrole C₂, C₅-H; bridging ph-C₂, C₃, C₅, C₆-H; quinoline-C₄, C₅, C₆, C₇, C₈-H and ph-C₂, C₃, C₅, C₆-H).

(4-(1H-pyrrol-1-yl)phenyl)(3-(4-aminophenyl)-5-(2-chloroquinolin-3-yl)-4,5-dihydro-1H-pyrazol-1-yl)methanone (5f):

IR (KBr) ν_{\max} , cm^{-1} : 3343 (NH₂), 2956 (Ar-H), 1665 (C=O), 1580 (C=N). $^1\text{H NMR}$ (400 MHz, DMSO- d_6) δ (ppm): 1.24 (s, 2H, pyrazoline-C₄-H), 2.55 (s, 1H pyrazoline-C₃-H), 5.92 (s, 2H, NH₂, phenyl-C₄-H), 6.67 (s, 2H, pyrrole-C₃, C₄-H), 6.69-8.09 (m, 15H, pyrrole C₂, C₅-H; bridging ph-C₂, C₃, C₅, C₆-H; quinoline-C₄, C₅, C₆, C₇, C₈-H and ph-C₂, C₃, C₅, C₆-H). MS (EI): m/z = found 491.09[M⁺]; calcd. 491.98.

(4-(1H-pyrrol-1-yl)phenyl)(5-(2-chloroquinolin-3-yl)-3-(3-nitrophenyl)-4,5-dihydro-1H-pyrazol-1-yl)methanone (5g):

IR (KBr) ν_{\max} , cm^{-1} : 2955 (Ar-H), 1663 (C=O), 1575 (C=N).

(4-(1H-pyrrol-1-yl)phenyl)(5-(2-chloroquinolin-3-yl)-3-(4-hydroxyphenyl)-4,5-dihydro-1H-pyrazol-1-yl)methanone (5h):

IR (KBr) ν_{\max} , cm^{-1} : 2956 (Ar-H), 1609 (C=N). $^1\text{H NMR}$ (400 MHz, DMSO- d_6) δ (ppm): 1.24 (s, 2H, pyrazoline-C₄-H), 2.56 (s, 1H pyrazoline-C₃-H), 6.30 (s, 2H, pyrrole-C₃, C₄-H), 7.24-7.98 (m, 15H, pyrrole C₂, C₅-H; bridging ph-C₂, C₃, C₅, C₆-H; quinoline-C₄, C₅, C₆, C₇, C₈-H and ph-C₂, C₃, C₅, C₆-H), 9.77 (s, 1H, -OH, phenyl-C₄-H).

(4-(1H-pyrrol-1-yl)phenyl)(5-(2-chloroquinolin-3-yl)-3-(p-tolyl)-4,5-dihydro-1H-pyrazol-1-yl)methanone (5i):

IR (KBr) ν_{\max} , cm^{-1} : 2955 (Ar-H), 1675 (C=O), 1605 (C=N).

(4-(1H-pyrrol-1-yl)phenyl)(5-(2-chloroquinolin-3-yl)-3-(3-methoxyphenyl)-4,5-dihydro-1H-pyrazol-1-yl)methanone (5j):

IR (KBr) ν_{\max} , cm^{-1} : 2955 (Ar-H), 1673 (C=O), 1604 (C=N). $^1\text{H NMR}$ (400 MHz, DMSO- d_6) δ (ppm): 0.88 (s, 2H, pyrazoline-C₄-H), 1.24 (s, 1H pyrazoline-C₃-H), 3.92 (s, 3H, -OCH₃) 6.31 (t, 2H, pyrrole-C₃, C₄-H), 7.01-8.11 (m, 15H, pyrrole C₂, C₅-H; bridging ph-C₂, C₃, C₅, C₆-H; quinoline-C₄, C₅, C₆, C₇, C₈-H and ph-C₂, C₃, C₅, C₆-H).

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Synthetic and spectral study

In present work, we have to combined quinoline with pyrazole, for that precursor substituted chalcone derivatives (3a-j) were prepared by reaction between 2-chloroquinoline carbaldehyde (1) with various substituted acetophenones (2a-j) in 40% NaOH and ethanol. Further, 3a-j was reacted with 4-pyrrol-1-yl-benzoic acid hydrazide (4) yielded the corresponding pyrrolyl-pyrazoline methanone derivatives (5a-j). The structures of all the compounds synthesized were established on the basis of analytical and spectral data. All the compounds were screened for *in vitro* antibacterial activity against Gram-positive and Gram-negative bacteria and antitubercular activity against *Mycobacterium tuberculosis* H₃₇Rv. The newly synthesized compounds exhibited significant MIC values compared to standard drugs.

The IR spectrum of 5a exhibited bands at 1665 cm⁻¹, 1606 cm⁻¹ which were due to (-C=O), (-C=N) stretching frequencies respectively. The aromatic (C-H) absorption band displayed at 3057 cm⁻¹. In the ¹H NMR spectrum of 5a showed singlet at δ 1.41 due to two proton of pyrazoline-C₄-H. Singlet at δ 2.34 due to one proton of pyrazoline-C₃-H, singlet at δ 6.39 due to two proton of pyrrole-C₃, C₄-H and multiplet exhibited at δ 7.18-7.90 due to fifteen proton of pyrrole C₂, C₅-H; bridging phenyl-C₂, C₃, C₅, C₆-H; quinoline-C₄, C₅, C₆, C₇, C₈-H and ph-C₂, C₃, C₄, C₅, C₆-H. Mass spectrum of 5a exhibited molecular ion peak 476.20. The physicochemical data for all synthesized compounds are compiled in Table 1.

Table 1. Physical data of the synthesized compounds.

Comp	R	Yield	MP (°C)	Molecular formula	Molecular weight
5a	H	95	150-152	C ₁₉ H ₂₁ N ₄ OCl	356.5
5b	4- Br	92	180-183	C ₁₉ H ₂₀ N ₄ OClBr	435.4
5c	4-NO ₂	86	160-162	C ₁₉ H ₂₀ N ₅ O ₃ Cl	401.5
5d	4-OCH ₃	82	138-140	C ₂₀ H ₂₃ N ₄ O ₂ Cl	386.5
5e	4-Cl	96	140-144	C ₁₉ H ₂₁ N ₄ OCl ₂	391
5f	4-NH ₂	93	120-122	C ₁₉ H ₂₂ N ₅ OCl	371.5
5g	3-NO ₂	85	154-156	C ₁₉ H ₂₁ N ₅ O ₃ Cl	402.5
5h	4-OH	94	116-118	C ₁₉ H ₂₂ N ₄ O ₂ Cl	373.5
5i	4-CH ₃	98	210-212	C ₂₀ H ₂₃ N ₄ OCl	370.5
5j	3-OCH ₃	90	165-167	C ₂₀ H ₂₃ N ₄ O ₂ Cl	386.5

Antibacterial activity

The MIC determination of the tested compounds was carried out simultaneously in comparison with ciprofloxacin, norfloxacin against Gram-positive (*Staphylococcus aureus* and *Bacillus subtilis*). Gram-negative bacteria (*Vibrio cholerae* and *Escherichia coli*) by broth micro dilution method [19, 20]. Serial dilutions of the test compounds and reference drugs were prepared in Mueller-Hinton broth. Drugs (10 mg) were dissolved in dimethylsulfoxide (DMSO, 1 mL). Further progressive dilutions were done to obtain final concentrations of 0.2, 0.4, 0.8, 1.6, 3.125, 6.25, 12.5, 25, 50 and 100 µg mL⁻¹. The tubes were inoculated with 10⁵ cfu mL⁻¹ (colony forming unit/mL) and incubated at 37 C for 18 h. The MIC was the lowest concentration of the tested compound that yield no visible growth on the plate. To ensure that the solvent had no effect on the bacterial growth, a control was performed with the test medium supplemented with DMSO at the same dilutions as used in the experiments and DMSO had no effect on the microorganisms in the concentrations studied. The MIC values are given in µg/ml. Ciprofloxacin and norfloxacin were used as standard drugs. The preliminary results of antibacterial activities are depicted in Table 2. Compounds showed antibacterial activity between MIC of 100-0.8 µg/ml.

Table 2. In vitro antibacterial activity of the synthesized compounds.

Compounds	R	Antibacterial activity MIC (µg/ml)			
		Gram negative		Gram positive	
		<i>V. cholera</i>	<i>E. coli</i>	<i>S. aureus</i>	<i>B. subtilis</i>
5a	H	6.25	25	0.8	25
5b	4- Br	25	6.25	0.8	25
5c	4-NO ₂	6.25	12.5	0.8	12.5
5d	4-OCH ₃	0.8	0.8	6.5	6.5
5e	4-Cl	25	6.5	25	12.5
5f	4-NH ₂	6.25	0.8	6.25	25
5g	3-NO ₂	25	6.25	12.5	0.8
5h	4-OH	6.25	0.8	0.8	6.25
5i	4-CH ₃	12.5	25	6.25	6.25
5j	3-OCH ₃	6.25	25	12.5	0.8
Norfloxacin		2		2	
Ciprofloxacin		2		2	

The compounds 5a, 5b, and 5c shows good MIC value of 0.8 µg/ml against gram positive bacteria such as *S. aureus*. The compound 5d shows significant MIC value of 0.8 µg/ml against gram negative bacteria such as *V. cholerae* and *E. coli* and compound 5h shows good MIC value of 0.8 µg/ml against both gram positive and gram negative bacteria like *S. aureus* and *E. coli* respectively while other compounds in the series showed moderate antibacterial activity, so the combination of heterocycles (quinoline, pyrazole and pyrrole) can be considered as potential candidates for antibacterial activity against both Gram-positive and Gram-negative organisms after structural modification.

Antitubercular activity

MIC values were determined for the newly synthesized compounds against *M. tuberculosis* strain H₃₇Rv using the Microplate Alamar Blue assay (MABA) [21] using isoniazid as the standard drug. The 96 wells plate received 100 µl of Middlebrook 7H9 broth and serial dilution of compounds were made directly on the plate with drug concentrations of 0.2, 0.4, 0.8, 1.6, 3.125, 6.25, 12.5, 25, 50 and 100 µg/ml. Plates were covered and sealed with parafilm and incubated at 37°C for 5 days. Then, 25 µl of freshly prepared 1:1 mixture of almar blue reagent and 10% Tween 80 was added to the plate and incubated for 24 h. A blue color in the well was interpreted as no bacterial growth and pink color was scored as growth. The MIC was defined as the lowest drug concentration, which prevented color change from blue to pink. Compounds 5a, 5c, 5e, 5f, 5g, 5h, and 5i exhibited the highly significant antitubercular activity with MIC 1.6 µg/ml, compound 5j showed MIC value at 3.125 µg/ml, compound 5b showed MIC value at 6.25 µg/ml and compound 5d showed MIC value at 12.5 µg/ml against *M. tuberculosis*. The antitubercular activity (MIC) data are compiled in Table 3.

Table 3. Preliminary *in vitro* antitubercular activity results of newly synthesized compounds against *M. tuberculosis* H37RV.

Compounds	R	Minimum inhibitory concentration (MIC). (µg/ml)
5a	H	1.6
5b	4- Br	6.25
5c	4-NO ₂	1.6
5d	4-OCH ₃	12.5
5e	4-Cl	1.6
5f	4-NH ₂	1.6
5g	3-NO ₂	1.6
5h	4-OH	1.6
5i	4-CH ₃	1.6
5j	3-OCH ₃	3.12

SCHEME-I Synthetic route for quinoline pyrazoles

R = a) -H, b) 4-Br, c) 4-NO₂, d) 4-OCH₃, e) 4-Cl, f) 4-NH₂, g) 3-NO₂, h) 4-OH, i) 4-CH₃, j) 3-OCH₃

CONCLUSIONS

Novel pyrrolyl-pyrazoline methanone derivatives (5a-j) were synthesized by reacting mixture of substituted chalcones (3a-j) and 4-pyrrol-1-yl benzoic acid hydrazide (4) in ethanol. The reaction mixture was heated under reflux for 16 h on a water bath followed by addition of ice cold water at room temperature and mixture was kept overnight resulting in the formations of substituted pyrrolyl-pyrazoline methanone derivatives. The synthesized compound showed MIC against gram negative bacteria and gram positive bacteria ranging from 0.8 to 100 µg/ml. The compounds 5a, 5b, and 5c shows good MIC value of 0.8 µg/ml against gram positive bacteria such as *S. aureus*. The compound 5d shows significant MIC value of 0.8 µg/ml against gram negative bacteria such as *V. cholera* and *E. coli* and compound 5h shows good MIC value of 0.8 µg/ml against both gram positive and gram negative bacteria like *S. aureus* and *E. coli* respectively while other compounds in the series showed moderate antibacterial activity. The synthesized compound showed MIC range of antitubercular activity extend from 1.6 to 12.5 µg/ml against *M. tuberculosis* strain H₃₇Rv. Compounds 5a, 5c, 5e, 5f, 5g, 5h, and 5i exhibited the highly significant antitubercular activity with MIC 1.6 µg/ml, compound 5j showed MIC value at 3.125 µg/ml, compound 5b showed MIC value at 6.25 µg/ml and compound 5d showed MIC value at 12.5 µg/ml against *M. tuberculosis*, based on screening results, it can be concluded that combination of heterocycles with different substituents like methoxy, bromo, chloro, nitro, hydroxy and amine helps to improve antibacterial and antitubercular activity of synthesized compounds.

Conflict of interest

Authors do not have any conflict of interest.

List of Abbreviations

BCG	Bacillus Calmettee Guerin
°C	Degree centigrade
Cfu	Colony forming unit
CDCl ₃	Deuterated chloroform
Comp	Compound
DMSO	Dimethyl sulphoxide
FTIR	Fourier Transform Infrared
Gm	Gram
h	Hour
HIV	Human Immunodeficiency Virus
M.P.	Melting Point
MDR	Multi Drug Resistant
MTB	Mycobacterium tuberculosis
Mg	Milligram
ml	Millilitre
MABA	Microplate Almar Blue Assay
MDR-TB	Multi-Drug Resistant Tuberculosis
Min.	Minutes
Mol	Mole
MIC	Minimum inhibitory concentration
NM	Nanometre
No	Number
NMR	Nuclear Magnetic Resonance
%	Percentage
Ppm	Parts per million
TLC	Thin Layer Chromatography
TMS	Tetra methyl silane
TB	Tuberculosis
UV	Ultra Violet
XDR-TB	Extensively Drug Resistant Tuberculosis
W/W	Weight by Weight
WHO	World Health Organization
Wt	Weight

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